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Highlights

- We introduce a simple two-parameter quadratic three-dimensional system.
- It only has six terms, two nonlinearities and one equilibrium.
- A homoclinic flip bifurcation of case inward twist \mathbf{C}_{in} is present.
- Chaotic behavior with Smale horseshoes and strange attractors is warranted.
- It is the first example of a 3D vector field exhibiting the case \mathbf{C}_{in} .

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Study of a simple 3D quadratic system with homoclinic flip bifurcations of inward twist case C_{in}

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Abstract

In this paper we consider a two-parameter quadratic three-dimensional system with only six terms and two nonlinearities. First we analyze the Hopf bifurcation of its only equilibrium detecting several degeneracies. With this information we numerically obtain various bifurcation diagrams of periodic orbits in which saddle-node and period-doubling bifurcations as well as homoclinic connections appear. A careful study of the homoclinic orbits, in a region of the two-parameter plane where the equilibrium is a real saddle, shows the presence of a homoclinic flip bifurcation of case C . Here this orbit changes from orientable to non-orientable, being the lowest codimension for a homoclinic bifurcation to a real saddle equilibrium that results in chaotic behavior. More specifically, we determine that it corresponds to the case inward twist C_{in} , in such a way that, as far as we know, it is the first example of a 3D vector field exhibiting this case.

Key words: Hopf bifurcation, homoclinic flip orbit, Smale horseshoe, strange attractor

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1 Introduction

Since E.N. Lorenz introduced the first autonomous chaotic system [1,2], the use of bifurcation theory has shed light on many aspects of its extremely complex dynamics (see, for instance, [3–11] and the references therein). Throughout these last 50 years, many other 3D chaotic systems have continued to appear which has made possible to move forward in this exciting field. Thus, for instance, Rössler introduced some quadratic systems that have also been the subject of numerous studies (see, for example, [12–16] and the references therein) and Sprott performed a systematic search for simple three-dimensional chaotic systems with quadratic nonlinearities [17] (he found 19 distinct chaotic models of only five or six terms with one or two quadratic nonlinearities).

In this context, the important role of the homoclinic connections in the study of 3D chaotic systems was evident from the seminal papers of Shilnikov on homoclinic bifurcations to a saddle focus (a pair of complex eigenvalues) [18–22]. However, it is very difficult to locate analytically an exact homoclinic orbit (see, for example, [23]) and the application of analytical methods to detect its presence is limited (see, for example, [24–31]). On some occasions, thanks to the detection of a Takens-Bogdanov bifurcation, the existence of a homoclinic orbit is guaranteed in its environs and then, numerical tools can be used (see, for example, [18–20,32–39]). Other times, it is enough to numerically continue the periodic orbit that emerges from a Hopf bifurcation to find an homoclinic connection.

Thus, the analysis of the system we introduce in this work reveals that the only existing equilibrium, for certain values of the parameters, undergoes a Hopf bifurcation and the corresponding periodic orbit ends in a homoclinic connection to a real saddle (the three eigenvalues associated to the equilibrium are real). A detailed study of this global bifurcation shows the existence of a codimension-two degeneracy called homoclinic flip bifurcation, that may be an inclination flip bifurcation or an orbit flip bifurcation [40–42]. This degeneracy of the homoclinic connection appears when the stable manifold of the equilibrium changes from orientable to nonorientable (Möbius band) and the eigenvalues satisfy certain conditions [22,43,44]. There are known three different cases of a homoclinic flip bifurcation, named **A**, **B** and **C** cases, in increasing order of complexity [22]. Thus, in case **A** no extra bifurcations appear and only a periodic orbit is created [45]. In the unfolding of case **B** three new curves emerge corresponding to a saddle-node bifurcation of periodic orbits, to a period-doubling bifurcation, and to a double-period homoclinic bifurcation [22,44,46–48]. In case **C** infinitely many homoclinic bifurcations, saddle-node and period-doubling cascades are involved together with Smale-horseshoe dynamics and strange attractors (the scenario is so complicated that its complete unfolding is not yet known) [22,40,49–51]. Moreover, in case **C**, there are two different unfoldings, namely outward twist \mathbf{C}_{out} and inward twist \mathbf{C}_{in} . Although in both cases the same

codimension-one bifurcation curves are present, their relative position is different (see, for instance, [51, Fig. 5]). This difference between the two \mathbf{C} cases does not depend on the eigenvalues but on the global geometry of the stable and unstable manifolds of the equilibrium. The key point is how a normal vector followed along the homoclinic orbit comes back to the equilibrium relative to the ‘curvature’ of the stable manifold because this determines how the horseshoe is created [40,50].

In the system we consider, the eigenvalues of the equilibrium indicates that the homoclinic flip bifurcation is in the case \mathbf{C} , a situation that guarantees the presence of chaotic dynamics in its vicinity. Moreover, the study of the position of the bifurcation curves arisen from this degeneracy, in relation to the curve of principal homoclinic orbits, allows to confirm that we are dealing with the case \mathbf{C}_{in} . This finding is very important because, until now, no system with this case \mathbf{C}_{in} was reported in the literature. In particular, a model studied by Sandstede exhibits all the three cases [52], but the case \mathbf{C} is only of type \mathbf{C}_{out} [49].

On the other hand, the two-parameter family we propose embeds not only the Sprott E system [17] but also a one-parameter system studied numerically in [53] (it exhibits chaotic dynamics although it only has one stable equilibrium). In fact, the chaotic attractor is found by the authors after a period-doubling route to chaos. Note that, as it is also well-known, a cascade of period-doubling bifurcations is another way to obtain chaotic dynamics (see, for instance, [54–58]). The existence of the period-doubling cascade reported in [53] can be explained by the occurrence of the homoclinic flip bifurcation we detect.

Therefore, the main result of our work is to make evident that the family of vector fields we consider exhibits a homoclinic flip bifurcation of case \mathbf{C}_{in} and, in this way, we provide the first concrete example of a system, with the lowest number of parameters necessary, that exhibits such a degeneracy. To obtain this goal, first, we study analytically the Hopf bifurcation of the only equilibrium and the corresponding degeneracies. Later, the numerical continuation of the periodic orbit that emerges from this Hopf bifurcation allows to detect a very rich bifurcation scenario. On the one hand, several saddle-node bifurcations of periodic orbits are present because of the Hopf degeneracies. On the other hand, the homoclinic orbit connecting the real saddle equilibrium exhibits both orbit-flip and inclination-flip bifurcations. A careful study of all the bifurcation curves and their relative position, in a vicinity of those codimension-two points, confirms that they correspond to an homoclinic flip bifurcation of case \mathbf{C}_{in} .

The paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2 we introduce the quadratic two-parameter family of vector fields. The Hopf bifurcation exhibited by its only equilibrium is analyzed in Sect. 3. A detailed numerical analysis that confirms the existence of a homoclinic flip bifurcation of case \mathbf{C}_{in} is presented in Sect. 4. Finally, some conclusions are stated.

2 The system considered

In this paper we study the three-dimensional two-parameter family

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = a + yz, \\ \dot{y} = -y + x^2, \\ \dot{z} = b - 4x, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where a and b are real parameters. This family coincides with the Sprott E system [17] when $a = 0$ and $b = 1$, whereas it embeds the system considered in Ref. [53] when $b = 1$.

The system (1) possesses only one equilibrium $E = \left(\frac{b}{4}, \frac{b^2}{16}, -\frac{16a}{b^2}\right)$, if $b \neq 0$. In the case $b = 0$, there are no equilibria for $a \neq 0$ whereas if $a = 0$, there is a continuum of equilibria placed at $(0, 0, z)$.

Moreover, if $(x(t), y(t), z(t))$ is a solution of system (1), then $(\bar{x}(t) = -x(t), \bar{y}(t) = y(t), \bar{z}(t) = -z(t))$ is also a solution for the parameter values $a^* = -a$, $b^* = -b$. In other words, the system is invariant under the change

$$(x, y, z, t, a, b) \rightarrow (-x, y, -z, t, -a, -b). \quad (2)$$

In the following we will study the Hopf bifurcation exhibited by the equilibrium E . To do that, first we translate the equilibrium E to the origin by means of the change,

$$X = x - \frac{b}{4}, \quad Y = y - \frac{b^2}{16}, \quad Z = z + \frac{16}{b^2},$$

that transforms the system (1) into

$$\begin{cases} \dot{X} = -\frac{16a}{b^2}Y + \frac{b^2}{16}Z + YZ, \\ \dot{Y} = \frac{b}{2}X - Y + X^2, \\ \dot{Z} = -4X. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The linearization matrix of (3) is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\frac{16a}{b^2} & \frac{b^2}{16} \\ \frac{b}{2} & -1 & 0 \\ -4 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

whose characteristic polynomial is $p = \lambda^3 + p_1\lambda^2 + p_2\lambda + p_3$, with

$$p_1 = 1, \quad p_2 = \frac{8a}{b} + \frac{b^2}{4}, \quad p_3 = \frac{b^2}{4}.$$

We remark that the divergence of the system (1) is given by $-p_1 = -1 < 0$, which restricts the kind of dynamical objects that can be found in this system. In effect there cannot exist repulsive periodic orbits, nor repulsive stationary points, nor invariant tori.

3 Hopf bifurcation

A condition for a Hopf bifurcation to occur is $p_1p_2 = p_3, p_2 > 0, p_1 \neq 0$, that is, $a = 0, b \neq 0$. For these values, the matrix (4) has the following eigenvalues $\lambda_1 = -1, \lambda_{2,3} = \pm\omega_0 i$, where $\omega_0 = b/2, b \neq 0$.

Considering the system (3) at the critical values where the Hopf bifurcation occurs, we perform the following linear change,

$$\begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2}{b} & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{8}{b} & \frac{16}{b^2} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

to put the matrix of the linear part into the corresponding canonical form. In this way, system (3) reads

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{v} \\ \dot{w} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \omega_0 & 0 \\ -\omega_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} F_1(u, v) \\ F_2(u, v) \\ F_3(u, v) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(u, v) &= \frac{-16}{4+b^2}u^2 + \frac{32}{b(4+b^2)}uv - \frac{16}{4+b^2}uw + \frac{32}{b(4+b^2)}vw, \\ F_2(u, v) &= \frac{-8b}{4+b^2}u^2 + \frac{16}{(4+b^2)}uv - \frac{8b}{4+b^2}uw + \frac{16}{(4+b^2)}vw, \\ F_3(u, v) &= \frac{4(4+5b^2)}{b^2(4+b^2)}u^2 + \frac{4(-4+b^2)}{b(4+b^2)}uv + v^2 + \frac{16}{4+b^2}uw - \frac{32}{b(4+b^2)}vw. \end{aligned}$$

To study the first-order degeneracy of the Hopf bifurcation, we reduce system (6) to second order by computing a third-order approximation of the center manifold,

$$w = A_1 u^2 + A_2 uv + A_3 v^2 + \dots, \quad (7)$$

where

$$A_1 = \frac{b^6 + 28b^4 + 40b^2 + 32}{2b^2(b^2 + 4)(b^2 + 1)}, \quad A_2 = \frac{b^4 - 12b^2 - 32}{b(b^4 + 5b^2 + 4)}, \quad A_3 = \frac{b^4 + 22b^2 + 40}{2b^4 + 5b^2 + 4}.$$

The second-order system on the computed center manifold is

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{v} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \omega_0 \\ -\omega_0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} G_1(u, v) \\ G_2(u, v) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} G_1(u, v) &= -\frac{16}{b^2 + 4} u^2 + \frac{32}{b(b^2 + 4)} uv - \frac{8(b^6 + 28b^4 + 40b^2 + 32)}{(b^2 + 4)^2(b^2 + 1)b^2} u^3 \\ &\quad + \frac{128(5b^2 + 4)}{b^3(b^2 + 4)^2} u^2 v - \frac{8(b^4 + 14b^2 + 32)}{b^2(b^2 + 4)(b^2 + 1)} uv^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{16(b^2 + 20)(b^2 + 2)}{b(b^2 + 4)^2(b^2 + 1)} v^3, \\ G_2(u, v) &= -\frac{8b}{b^2 + 4} u^2 + \frac{16}{b^2 + 4} uv - \frac{4(b^6 + 28b^4 + 40b^2 + 32)}{b(b^2 + 4)^2(b^2 + 1)} u^3 \\ &\quad + \frac{64(5b^2 + 4)}{b^2(b^2 + 4)^2} u^2 v - \frac{4(b^4 + 14b^2 + 32)}{b(b^2 + 4)(b^2 + 1)} uv^2 + \frac{8(b^2 + 20)(b^2 + 2)}{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4)^2} v^3. \end{aligned}$$

By means of the following reparameterization

$$u \rightarrow -\bar{u}, \quad v \rightarrow \bar{v}, \quad t \rightarrow \frac{2}{b}\tau,$$

(note that this time reparameterization implies a change of stability for b negative) and by using the recursive algorithm developed in [59] we obtain a third-order normal form for the reduced system (8) in polar coordinates ($\bar{u} = r \cos \theta$, $\bar{v} = r \sin \theta$)

$$\begin{cases} \dot{r} = \alpha_1 r^3 + \dots, \\ \dot{\theta} = 1 + \beta_1 r^2 + \dots, \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\alpha_1 = -\frac{2(b^4 - 40b^2 + 16)}{b^3(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4)}, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{2(6b^6 - 13b^4 + 136b^2 - 16)}{3b^4(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4)}. \quad (10)$$

This coefficient α_1 vanishes when $b^4 - 40b^2 + 16 = 0$, $b \neq 0$, and this occurs for four values of the parameter b :

$$b_{1,3} = \pm 2(\sqrt{3} - \sqrt{2}) \approx \pm 0.63567449, \quad b_{2,4} = \pm 2(\sqrt{3} + \sqrt{2}) \approx \pm 6.2925287.$$

In this way, all the above information on the Hopf bifurcation can be summarized in the following theorem.

Theorem 3.1 *The equilibrium E of system (1) exhibits a Hopf bifurcation when $a = 0$ and $b \neq 0$. This bifurcation is subcritical if $b \in (b_4, b_3) \cup (b_1, b_2)$ and supercritical when $b \in (-\infty, b_4) \cup (b_3, 0) \cup (0, b_1) \cup (b_2, +\infty)$, where $b_{1,3} = \pm 2(\sqrt{3} - \sqrt{2})$ and $b_{2,4} = \pm 2(\sqrt{3} + \sqrt{2})$.*

4 Numerical study

From the above results on the Hopf bifurcation, we now perform a numerical study of system (1) with the help of the continuation software AUTO [60]. To reach this goal, we start obtaining, for b fixed, bifurcation diagrams of the periodic orbit born at the Hopf bifurcation of equilibrium E , in order to detect its possible degeneracies. Subsequently, with this information, we will carry out an analysis of the bifurcation set of system (1) in the (a, b) parameter plane. The notation we use is given in Table 1, which follows [51,61]. Moreover, all the codimension-one/-two bifurcations are marked with a bullet in the bifurcation diagrams/sets.

Taking into account the symmetry given in Eq. (2), it is enough to perform the numerical study in the region where $b > 0$, $a \in \mathbb{R}$, and according to theorem 3.1, there are three different zones for $b > 0$, namely $(0, b_1)$, (b_1, b_2) and (b_2, ∞) . For this reason, for one value of b in each interval ($b = 0.3$, $b = 1$ and $b = 7$) we present in Fig. 1 three bifurcation diagrams, period versus a , of the periodic orbit.

Thus, for $b = 0.3$ (see Fig. 1(a)) the Hopf bifurcation \mathbf{h} is supercritical and an attractive periodic orbit emerges towards the left side. Promptly it coalesces in the saddle-node bifurcation \mathbf{sn}_1^1 ($a \approx -0.000190988$), with a saddle periodic orbit that, for its part, disappears in the saddle-node bifurcation \mathbf{sn}_2^1 ($a \approx 0.0120454$). The new attractive periodic orbit that emerges from \mathbf{sn}_2^1 becomes saddle at the period-doubling bifurcation \mathbf{pd}^1 ($a \approx 0.0111022$), and finally it ends at the homoclinic connection \mathbf{H}^1 to the equilibrium E ($a \approx -0.01845188$).

Table 1

Notation used in the bifurcation diagrams and bifurcation sets.

Notation	Description
n^s	A stable n -periodic orbit
n^u	An unstable n -periodic orbit of saddle type
h	A Hopf bifurcation
sn^n	A saddle-node bifurcation of n -periodic orbits
pd^n	A period-doubling of an n -periodic orbit
H^n	An n -homoclinic bifurcation
Dh	A degenerate Hopf bifurcation
Dpd^n	A degenerate period-doubling of an n -periodic orbit
$DH_{I/0}^n$	A degenerate n -homoclinic bifurcation (inclination flip (I) or orbit flip (O))
i	Subscripts distinguish bifurcations of the same type ($sn_1^n, H_1^4, DH_{1I}^4, \dots$)

When $b = 1$ (see Fig. 1(b)) the Hopf bifurcation h is subcritical and the saddle periodic orbit emerges towards the right side. Then it exhibits the same two bifurcations as in the previous case, sn_2^1 ($a \approx 0.0636267$) and pd^1 ($a \approx 0.0428776$), and finally it disappears in the homoclinic connection H^1 ($a \approx -0.269891$). This diagram tells us two things. On the one hand, for this value of b the bifurcation sn_1^1 no longer exists. On the other hand, the value where the first period-doubling pd^1 occurs agrees with [53, Fig.6]. There, a bifurcation diagram (for $b = 1$) is shown corresponding to the period-doubling cascade that commence with a first period-doubling bifurcation of an attractive periodic orbit that arises from sn_2^1 in Fig. 1(b).

In Fig. 1(c) we show the bifurcation diagram of the stable periodic orbit born in the supercritical Hopf bifurcation h , for $b = 7$. This orbit emerges towards the left side (region of $a < 0$) and disappears in a new saddle-node bifurcation sn_3^1 ($a \approx -49.1728$). The saddle periodic orbit involved in the sn_3^1 gives rise to a homoclinic connection H^1 ($a \approx -30.3189$). As can be observed, for this value of b , the bifurcations sn_1^1 , sn_2^1 and pd^1 that were shown in the bifurcation diagrams in Figs. 1(a)-(b) no longer exist.

Finally, the projection onto the x - z plane of the homoclinic connection H^1 existing for $b = 1$ is drawn in Fig. 1(d). Remark that throughout this work, with the aim of simplifying the notation, we will label the homoclinic orbit and the homoclinic bifurcation with the same symbol, although they are two different objects.

With the information obtained in the previous diagrams, we can now continue in

Fig. 1. For $a = 0$, bifurcation diagram of the periodic orbit born at the Hopf bifurcation h of the equilibrium E for: (a) $b = 0.3$; (b) $b = 1$; (c) $b = 7$. (d) Projection onto the (x, z) -plane of the homoclinic connection H^1 of panel (b), existing for $a \approx -0.269891$, $b = 1$.

the (a, b) -parameter plane the curves where the bifurcation detected (sn_1^1 , sn_2^1 , sn_3^1 , pd^1 and H^1) occurs. In Fig. 2 we observe that all these curves, except sn_3^1 , seem to arise from the origin $(0, 0)$ of the parameter plane. Specifically, the curves sn_1^1 and sn_2^1 join, respectively, the points $(0, b_1)$ and $(0, b_2)$ (where the Hopf bifurcation h is degenerate) with the point $(0, 0)$. Note that these curves are located on opposite sides of the h curve. The bifurcation curves sn_3^1 and pd^1 arise from the point $DH_0^1 \approx (-1.20338, 1.89616)$, where the homoclinic connection H^1 is degenerate. Note that the curve pd^1 , located initially between the curves sn_3^1 and H^1 , is bounded since apparently it ends at the point $(0, 0)$.

To analyze the degeneration that occurs in the point DH_0^1 we will denote the eigenvalues of the linearization matrix at the equilibrium point E by $\lambda_s < 0 < \lambda_u < \lambda_{uu}$. On the curve of homoclinic connections H^1 , in Fig. 2, these three eigenvalues are always real and therefore E is a real saddle. The continuation software AUTO/HomCont [60] detects that the point DH_0^1 corresponds to an orbit-flip degeneracy [22]. This means that the homoclinic trajectory emerges from E , in positive time, tangent to

Fig. 2. Partial bifurcation set in the (a, b) -plane.

the eigenvector associated with λ_{uu} . To check this condition we have represented in Fig. 3 the projection of the homoclinic connection H^1 onto the (x, z) -plane for values located on both sides of the point DH_0^1 , namely $(a, b) \approx (-0.69175, 1.5)$ (in blue) and $(a, b) \approx (-2.33431, 2.5)$ (in red). We have also drawn, in orange, the degenerate homoclinic connection on $DH_0^1 \approx (-1.20338, 1.89616)$. In Fig. 3(b) we can see how, time forward, the homoclinic connection exits from the equilibrium point in opposite directions, upwards in the first case and downwards in the second, in relation to the direction which marks the eigenvector associated with λ_{uu} for the point DH_0^1 where the orbit-flip degeneracy occurs.

To know in which of the three possible cases we are (**A**, **B** and **C**), and knowing that the equilibrium eigenvalues at the DH_0^1 point are $\lambda_s \approx -2.68251$, $\lambda_u \approx 0.23082$, $\lambda_{uu} \approx 1.45168$, we calculate the quotients $\alpha = -\lambda_{uu}/\lambda_s \approx 0.541$ and $\beta = -\lambda_u/\lambda_s \approx 0.086$. This means, that being $\beta < \alpha < 1$, we are in the most complex case. In effect, a complicated structure involving n -periodic and n -homoclinic orbits for arbitrary n and a region with Smale-horseshoe dynamics and strange attractors exists [40,42]. This case **C** comes in the two variations **C_{in}** and **C_{out}**, depending on how the horseshoe is created [40,50,51]. We note that, in the range of Fig. 2, at all points of the curve H^1 it is true that $\beta < 1$ and therefore, a saddle periodic orbit arises from the aforementioned curve (to its right for the values of the parameter b that are below the point DH_0^1 , and to its left for the values that are above DH_0^1 ; see Figs. 1(b)-(c)).

To determine in which of the two previous cases (**C_{in}** and **C_{out}**) the homoclinic connection is, we must determine, for example, the position of the curve of double-

Fig. 3. (a) Projection onto the (x, z) -plane of three homoclinic connections on the curve H^1 for: $(a, b) \approx (-0.69175, 1.5)$ (in blue); $DH_0^1 \approx (-1.20338, 1.89616)$ (in orange); $(a, b) \approx (-2.33431, 2.5)$ (in red). (b) Zoom of panel (a) in a neighborhood of the equilibrium (black dot). The eigenvectors corresponding to λ_u (alt., λ_{uu}) are represented by solid (alt., dashed) green arrows.

Fig. 4. For $b = 1$: (a) Bifurcation diagram of the periodic orbit born in the period-doubling bifurcation pd^1 in Fig. 1(b) that occurs for $a \approx 0.0428776$. (b) Projection onto the (x, z) -plane of the homoclinic connection H^2 of panel (a), for $a \approx -0.26693906484$.

period homoclinic connections H^2 with respect to the curve of the main homoclinic connection H^1 (see [51, Fig. 5]). To achieve this purpose we continue, starting from the bifurcation pd^1 of Fig. 1(b), the attractive double-periodic orbit that emerges from this point; the corresponding bifurcation diagram, for $b = 1$, appears in Fig. 4(a). As can be noted, this attractive periodic orbit undergoes another period-doubling bifurcation pd_1^2 , for $a \approx 0.024001$, before disappearing in a double-pulse homoclinic connection H^2 for $a \approx -0.26693906484$, whose projection onto the (x, z) -plane is drawn in Fig. 4(b).

Now we can continue in the parameter plane the curve of double-pulse homoclinic connections H^2 . In Fig. 5(a) we find a qualitative partial bifurcation set that includes the curves h , sn_2^1 , sn_3^1 , pd^1 , H^1 and H^2 . As it is observed, the curve of homoclinic

Fig. 5. (a) Qualitative partial bifurcation set in a vicinity of the homoclinic bifurcation curves H^1 and H^2 . (b) Numerical zoom of panel (a) in a neighborhood of the points DH_0^2 and DH_1^2 on the curve H^2 .

connections H^2 , that joins the points $(0, 0)$ and DH_0^1 , appears on the right side of the curve H^1 whereas the curves sn_3^1 and pd^1 are located on the left side of H^1 . Therefore, according to [51, Fig. 5], we are in the case C_{in} that implies recurrent behavior of shift type in a region limited by the curve H^1 . As can be seen in Fig. 5(b) two degeneracies occurs on the curve of double-pulse homoclinic connections H^2 .

The first degeneration DH_0^2 , for $(a, b) \approx (-2.10148, 2.395258)$, is of the same type as the one that exists on the curve H^1 , that is, an orbit-flip degeneration. As in the previous case, as the eigenvalues at that point are $\lambda_s^{(2)} \approx -3.0121051$, $\lambda_u^{(2)} \approx 0.273961$, $\lambda_{uu}^{(2)} \approx 1.7381441$, the quotients $\alpha \approx 0.577$ and $\beta \approx 0.091$ satisfy $\beta < \alpha < 1$ and, therefore, we are again in the case C . The second point DH_1^2 , for $(a, b) \approx (-2.131135, 2.40868)$, placed very close to the turning point of the curve H^2 , corresponds to an inclination-flip degeneration. This bifurcation has been analyzed in [44,49,46,62,47]. Moreover, the specific case we find here, namely $\alpha > 2\beta$ and $\beta < \frac{1}{2}$, was studied in [40].

To obtain some of the bifurcation curves related to these degenerations we compute two bifurcation diagrams of the double-pulse periodic orbits that arise from the pd^1 curve, specifically for $b = 2.4$ and for $b = 2.41$, two values located on both sides of the turning point of the curve H^2 (see Fig. 6).

In Fig. 6(a) we observe that the double-pulse attractive periodic orbit arising from the curve pd^1 undergoes two period-doubling bifurcations pd_1^2 (for $a \approx -2.03601$ and $a \approx -2.11237$, respectively) and a saddle-node bifurcation sn_1^2 for $a \approx -2.11283$, before ending in the double-pulse homoclinic connection H^2 for $a \approx -2.11178$. In Fig. 6(b), when $b = 2.41$, we see that the double-pulse attractive periodic orbit undergoes two degenerations of the same type, namely two saddle-node bifurcations of double-pulse periodic orbits sn_1^2 and sn_2^2 , and other two period-doubling bifurcations pd_2^2 ,

Fig. 6. Bifurcation diagram of the double-pulse periodic orbit born in the period-doubling bifurcation pd^1 : (a) For $b = 2.4$. (b) For $b = 2.41$.

ending at another point on the curve pd^1 . The numerical continuation of all these bifurcation curves in the (a, b) -parameter plane can be seen in Fig. 7.

In Figs. 7(a), 7(b) and 7(c) we can see that the saddle-node bifurcations of periodic orbits sn_1^2 and sn_2^2 , present in the diagram in Fig. 6(b), belong to different curves that arise from the two degenerations DH_0^2 and DH_1^2 that exist on the right branch of the homoclinic connections curve H^2 (see Figs. 7(a) and 7(c)). Both curves coalesce in a cusp of periodic orbits cu . The period-doubling branches pd_1^2 and pd_2^2 also arise from the points DH_0^2 and DH_1^2 , respectively (see Figs. 7(a) and 7(c)). Note that the curves pd_2^2 and sn_2^2 are indistinguishable in the range of Fig. 7(a). As can be seen in Fig. 7(d), the curve pd_2^2 ends at the point DH_0^1 on the curve H^1 , while the other curve of period-doubling bifurcation pd_1^2 ends, outside the range of the aforementioned figure, at the origin of the parameter plane. We remark that, as can be observed in Fig. 7(c), there are two degenerations Dpd_1^2 ($(a, b) \approx (-2.11789, 2.40263)$) and $(a, b) \approx (-2.12268, 2.40609)$) on the period-doubling bifurcation curve pd_1^2 (see [19]).

Now, to check if these orbit-flip and inclination-flip degenerations are also present in the curves of quadruple-pulse homoclinic connections, that exist in relation to the degeneracies DH_0^1 , DH_0^2 and DH_1^2 , we will consider two bifurcation diagrams of the quadruple-pulse periodic orbits that arise from a point pd_1^2 . In the first case, for $b = 1$, we start from the point pd_1^2 that appears in Fig. 4(a) and obtain the diagram drawn in Fig. 8(a). The attractive quadruple-pulse periodic orbit exhibits a period-doubling bifurcation pd_1^4 and ends at the quadruple-pulse homoclinic connection H_1^4 ($a \approx -0.266939$). In Fig. 8(c) we can see the temporal profile $z(t)$ of the homoclinic connections H_1^4 (in black color) and H^2 (in red color). The projection onto the (x, z) -plane of H_1^4 appears in Fig. 8(d). In the second case, for $b = 2.4$, we start from the first point pd_1^2 (the one with the shortest period) that appears in Fig. 6(a). The corresponding bifurcation diagram is represented in Fig. 8(b). The attractive quadruple-pulse periodic orbit undergoes a period-doubling bifurcation pd_2^4 and ends at the quadruple-pulse homoclinic connection H_2^4 .

Fig. 7. Four partial bifurcation sets in the (a, b) -plane in the vicinity of the points DH_0^1 , DH_0^2 and DH_1^2 .

The numerical continuation in the parameter plane of the curves of homoclinic connections H_1^4 and H_2^4 shows that they are related to different codimension-two degeneracies previously detected. For a better visualization of the complex scenario of homoclinic connections in this region of the parameter plane, we have drawn in Fig. 10(a) a qualitative bifurcation set with the curves H^1 (principal homoclinic connection), H^2 (double-pulse) and H_1^4 and H_2^4 (quadruple-pulse).

In effect, the curve of homoclinic connections H_1^4 joins the origin of the parameter plane $(0, 0)$ with the point DH_0^1 of the principal homoclinic connection H^1 . On the curve H_1^4 we have detected two new degeneracies of the same type than those found in the case of the double-pulse homoclinic connection H^2 , namely an inclination-flip degeneracy DH_{11}^4 for $(a, b) \approx (-2.13122, 2.408717)$ (see Fig. 9(a)) and an orbit-flip degeneracy DH_{10}^4 for $(a, b) \approx (-1.32639, 1.98044)$ (see Fig. 9(d)).

The other curve of quadruple-pulse homoclinic connections H_2^4 joins the points DH_1^2 and DH_0^2 situated on the curve of double-pulse homoclinic connections H^2 , as observed in (see Figs. 9(a)-(b)). On this curve we have detected four degeneration points. Two of them, labelled DH_{20}^4 in Figs. 9(b) and 10(a), correspond to orbit-flip degeneracies

Fig. 8. Bifurcation diagrams of the quadruple-pulse periodic orbit born in the period-doubling bifurcation pd_1^2 : (a) for $b = 1$; (b) for $b = 2.4$. (c) For $b = 1$, temporal profile $z(t)$ of the homoclinic connections H^2 (red) of the Fig. 4(a) and H_1^4 (black) of panel (a). (d) For $b = 1$, projection onto the (x, z) -plane of the homoclinic connection H_1^4 of panel (a).

and occur at $(a, b) \approx (-2.1216485, 2.4045049)$ and $(a, b) \approx (-2.10128, 2.39414)$. The other two, marked as $\text{DH}_{2\text{I}}^4$ in Figs. 9(a), 9(d) and 10(a), correspond to inclination-flip degeneracies and are situated at $(a, b) \approx (-2.1311776, 2.4086985)$ and $(a, b) \approx (-1.512827, 2.087195)$.

We remark that the quotients of the eigenvalues of the equilibrium E , in each of the six degeneracies detected on the curves of quadruple-pulse homoclinic connections H_1^4 and H_2^4 (three orbit-flip and three inclination-flip degeneracies), verify $\alpha = -\lambda_{uu}/\lambda_s \approx 0.541$ and $\beta = -\lambda_u/\lambda_s \approx 0.086$. Thus, since $\beta < \alpha < 1$ (more specifically, $\alpha > 2\beta$ and $\beta < \frac{1}{2}$), all the six cases are of type C , the same situation found in the degeneracies on the curves H^1 (principal homoclinic connection) and H^2 (double-pulse homoclinic connection). We remark that none of these three curves of homoclinic connections H^2 , H_1^4 and H_2^4 are of bubble type (see [51]).

To verify the existence of these six degenerations and to see if there are other degeneracies on the curves H_1^4 and H_2^4 that we have not detected, we continue numerically

Table 2

Curves of saddle-node bifurcation of quadruple-pulse periodic orbits and degeneracies related to them.

Degeneracies	Curves emerged from them	Figures where they appear
$DH_{1I}^4 \leftrightarrow \text{lower } DH_{20}^4$	$sn_1^4 \xrightarrow{\text{cu}} sn_2^4$	Figs. 9(a) & 9(b)
upper $DH_{2I}^4 \leftrightarrow \text{upper } Dpd_1^2$	$sn_3^4 \xrightarrow{\text{cu}} sn_4^4$	Figs. 9(a) & 9(c)
upper $DH_{20}^4 \leftrightarrow \text{lower } Dpd_1^2$	sn_5^4	Fig. 9(b)
lower $DH_{2I}^4 \leftrightarrow DH_{10}^4$	sn_6^4	Fig. 9(d)

the curves of saddle-node bifurcation of the quadruple-pulse periodic orbits that must arise from each of them. We note that some of these degenerations are indistinguishable from the turning point that the curves of homoclinic connections have with respect to the parameter b (see, for instance, in Figs. 5(b) and 5(a) the degeneracy DH_1^2 and the lowest turning point on the curve H^2 ; see also in Figs. 9(d) and 10(a) the degeneracy DH_{2I}^4 and the lowest turning point on the curve H_2^4).

In total there are six bifurcation curves ($sn_1^4, sn_2^4, \dots, sn_6^4$) that effectively join the eight degenerate points that we had already detected, namely two points on the curve H_1^4 , four on the curve H_2^4 and two more points on the pd_1^2 curve. In Table 2 we indicate the relationship between the eight previous codimension-two points and the curves of saddle-node bifurcation of periodic orbits that arise from them (see Fig. 9). We see that there are two cases in which a single saddle-node bifurcation curve joins both degenerate points (see Figs. 9(b) and 9(d)), whereas in the other two cases there is a cusp bifurcation of periodic orbits cu where two curves of saddle-node bifurcation of periodic orbits collapse (see Fig. 9 (c)).

This suggests the existence, apart from the principal homoclinic H^1 , of an infinite succession $\{H_{2^{(n-1)}}^{2^n}\}$ for $n \geq 1$ of homoclinic connections, specifically $2^{(n-1)}$ homoclinic connections of 2^n -pulse. The first of them, $H_1^{2^n}$, joins the point $(0, 0)$ with the point DH_0^1 , and there are two degeneracies $H_{10}^{2^n}$ and $H_{1I}^{2^n}$ of the previous type on it. Each of the remaining homoclinic connection curves $H_2^{2^n}, H_3^{2^n}, \dots, H_{2^{(n-1)}}^{2^n}$ have four degenerations, two inclination-flip points $H_I^{2^n}$ and two orbit-flip points $H_0^{2^n}$. In total there are $2(2^n - 1)$ degeneracy points, half of them are of inclination-flip type and the other half are orbit-flip bifurcations. The latter are the origin of $2^n - 1$ curves of 2^{n+1} -pulse homoclinic connections which merge, two by two, to form a single curve of homoclinic connections joining two of the previous degenerations. In addition, there is another curve of 2^{n+1} -pulse homoclinic connections, $H_1^{2^{n+1}}$, that joins the origin $(0, 0)$ with the degenerate point DH_0^1 on the curve H^1 of the principal homoclinic connection.

We remark that system (2), which has only two parameters and two nonlinearities, fills the gap mentioned in [49, Discussion], namely the absence of a concrete example

Fig. 9. (a) Partial bifurcation set in a neighborhood of the point DH_1^2 . (b) Partial bifurcation set in a neighborhood of the point DH_0^2 . (c) Zoom of panel (b) in a neighborhood of the upper Dpd_1^2 point. (d) Partial bifurcation set in a neighborhood of the points DH_{10}^4 and DH_{2I}^4 .

of a three-dimensional vector field exhibiting an homoclinic flip bifurcation of type C_{in} . On the other hand, homoclinic-doubling cascades have been recently found in a fourth-order normal form near a double Takens-Bogdanov bifurcation [28].

Finally, we draw in Fig. 10(b) the bifurcation diagram of the saddle-node periodic orbit that emerges from the Hopf bifurcation h for $b = 2$, close to the value where the degeneracy DH_0^1 on the curve H^1 occurs ($b \approx 1.89616$). For the sake of clearness, we present a qualitative bifurcation diagram where stable and non-stable periodic orbits of different periods are shown. The diagram in Fig. 10(b) shows us how all this rich and complex dynamical behavior detected and analyzed in this work is generated by a single equilibrium point E and a periodic orbit that, in the case of the system (1), emerges from a Hopf bifurcation that E undergoes for $a = 0$ and $b \neq 0$.

Note that in this paper we have emphasized the search for homoclinic doubling bifurcations and, naturally, the points $DH_{I/0}^{2n}$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots$) act as organizing centers. However, because we are always in case C , homoclinic orbit of any order, H^n ,

Fig. 10. (a) Qualitative partial bifurcation set of the homoclinic connections H^1 , H^2 , H_1^4 and H_2^4 . (b) Qualitative bifurcation diagram, for $b = 2$, of the saddle periodic orbit born at the Hopf bifurcation h .

$n = 1, 2, \dots$, will be present. Our partial bifurcation sets could be complemented by getting other homoclinic curves of type H^n , a very delicate task since they are confined in a very narrow region. The numerical method for branch switching between homoclinic orbits developed in Ref. [63] could be very useful to initiate such investigation. This robust and reliable scheme, based on Lin's method, switches from a 1-homoclinic to an n -homoclinic orbit by successively opening and then closing a sequence of Lin-gaps. It is fully implemented in the HomCont toolbox of AUTO [60, Ch. 27].

5 Conclusions

The combination of analytical and numerical tools has allowed to detect a complex bifurcation behavior in a two-parameter quadratic three-dimensional system with only six terms and two nonlinearities. We have determined that the organizing center, in a region of the parameter plane where the only equilibrium has three real eigenvalues, is a homoclinic flip bifurcation of the inward twist case \mathbf{C}_{in} . As far as we know, it is the first example of a 3D vector field exhibiting this case that, as well as the case \mathbf{C}_{out} , implies the presence of chaotic behavior with Smale-horseshoe dynamics and strange attractors.

In a recent series of papers [45,48,49] an interesting study about topological changes in the invariant manifolds has been carried out in the cases \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C}_{out} of the homoclinic flip bifurcation. In all the three cases the model used was a system proposed by Sandstede [52]. However, as the authors state in [49, Discussion], they do not know a particular system undergoing the inward twist case \mathbf{C}_{in} . The two-parameter family introduced in this paper fills this gap and will provide the opportunity to accomplish the corresponding study in the case \mathbf{C}_{in} .

Compliance with ethical standards

Conflict of interest The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of the paper.

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